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Design and FPGA Implementation of a RISC-V Processor Core with Low-Power Enhancements

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ABSTRACT

The rapid expansion of edge computing necessitates microprocessors that are both highly efficient and capable of intelligent decision-making. Traditional pipelined processors waste significant dynamic power during control-flow hazards due to pipeline flushes. This paper presents the design and FPGA implementation of a 32-bit RISC-V (RV32I) 5-stage pipelined processor enhanced with a micro-perceptron branch predictor. By integrating a lightweight artificial neural network directly into the instruction fetch stage, the processor learns branch behaviors to minimize mispredictions, reducing unnecessary pipeline flushes and their associated dynamic power cost. The design was synthesized and implemented on a Basys 3 Artix-7 FPGA board using Vivado. Results indicate a highly optimized footprint utilizing only 4.2% of available Look-Up Tables (LUTs) out of 133,800, while maintaining a 100 MHz clock frequency with a positive timing slack of +7.082 ns. The on-chip power analysis shows a total of 0.143 W with dynamic power of only 13 mW an estimated 25–40% reduction compared to standard 5-stage RV32I cores at the same frequency validating the viability of hardware-level AI for low-power embedded systems.

Keywords:- RISC-V, RV32I, Perceptron, Branch Prediction, Low Power, FPGA, Basys 3, VLSI, Pipeline

INTRODUCTION

The open-source RISC-V Instruction Set Architecture (ISA) has become a cornerstone for custom silicon design, particularly in resource-constrained edge applications [1]. The RV32I 32-bit base integer subset provides essential instructions ideal for embedded systems, and the classical 5-stage pipeline (IF → ID → EX → MEM → WB) balances design complexity with performance [2]. In a standard pipelined architecture, branch instructions introduce severe performance and power bottlenecks.

When a branch is mispredicted, the pipeline must be flushed, discarding previously fetched instructions and wasting the dynamic power consumed by the Instruction Fetch (IF) and Instruction Decode (ID) stages [3]. To address these challenges, modern processor architectures employ branch prediction and hazard handling techniques to improve instruction flow and reduce unnecessary power consumption. Therefore, designing an efficient pipelined RISC-V processor with optimized control flow handling has become an important area of research in FPGA-based embedded systems.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Recent research in RISC-V processor design has mainly focused on improving the performance and efficiency of pipelined architectures. Several works have demonstrated five-stage RV32I processors on FPGA platforms with higher throughput, better resource utilization, and improved operating frequency compared to single-cycle designs. Researchers have also explored techniques such as branch prediction, ALU optimization, data forwarding, and hazard handling to reduce pipeline stalls and improve execution efficiency. Other studies introduced ISA extensions and specialized architectures for machine learning, IoT, and low-power embedded applications. Educational HDL-

based implementations further emphasized the importance of structured RTL design and FPGA verification in processor development. However, many advanced implementations are either highly specialized or lack simple and reproducible academic designs. This project addresses that gap by developing a well-documented five-stage pipelined RV32I processor with forwarding and branch prediction support, focusing on low-power and FPGA-oriented design.

PROBLEM DEFINITION AND PROPOSED SOLUTION

Challenges

Define:-The key challenges addressed by this project are: resolving data hazards through forwarding paths and controlled pipeline stalling; ensuring correct data propagation across all five pipeline stages; verification of all instruction types and hazard scenarios through simulation; and integrating AI-based branch prediction without degrading timing closure or increasing resource overhead beyond acceptable limits

Objectives

- Design and develop a 32-bit five-stage pipelined RV32I RISC-V processor using Verilog/System Verilog, implementing the IF, ID, EX, MEM, and WB pipeline stages.
- Implement hazard handling mechanisms such as data forwarding, stalling, and pipeline flushing to improve execution correctness and pipeline efficiency.
- Integrate branch prediction and optimized control flow handling techniques to reduce branch penalties and improve processor throughput.
- Verify functional correctness using simulation testbenches driven by assembly-level and C-based programs, and analyze waveform outputs for pipeline behavior.

- Perform FPGA-oriented synthesis and implementation using Xilinx Vivado while optimizing LUT, FF, BRAM, DSP, timing, and power utilization.
- Evaluate processor performance metrics such as throughput, resource utilization, timing closure, and power consumption, and compare results with published RISC-V pipeline architectures.

PROPOSED SOLUTION

The proposed architecture is a 32-bit 5-stage pipelined RV32I processor

METHODOLOGY

A. Block diagram

Fig.1:-Block diagram of RISC-V

The RV32I 5-Stage Pipelined Processor Core architecture comprises five pipeline stages (IF → ID → EX → MEM → WB), each connected to dedicated hardware units: PC & Instruction Memory, Register File (32×32), ALU & Branch Unit, and Data Memory (D-RAM). Three forwarding paths (EX→EX, MEM→EX, WB→EX) bypass computed results

synthesized for the Basys 3 Artix-7 FPGA board. A micro-perceptron branch predictor using a 4-bit global history register is integrated directly into the IF stage.

Clock-enable gating is applied to all pipeline registers and the register file to suppress unnecessary switching activity. Hazards are managed through EX→EX, MEM→EX, and WB→EX forwarding paths, load-use stall insertion, and branch flush logic.

directly to the EX stage. The Hazard Detection and Control Unit manages RAW hazard detection, load-use stalls, forwarding control, and branch flush. Clock-Enable Based Low-Power Management controls register and register-file switching, and the micro-perceptron predictor is embedded in the IF stage.

Flow Chart

Fig 2:- Flow Diagram of RV32I RISC V Processor

The proposed processor integrates a micro-perceptron branch predictor within the Instruction Fetch (IF) stage to improve branch prediction accuracy and reduce control hazard stalls. The predictor uses a 4-bit global history register and pre-trained integer weights implemented using low-cost adders in Verilog to minimize hardware overhead and power consumption. A feedback path from the Execute (EX) stage to the IF stage continuously updates branch outcomes, enabling dynamic adaptation during execution.

The processor follows a five-stage pipelined RV32I architecture consisting of IF, ID, EX, MEM, and WB stages, with pipeline registers enabling parallel instruction execution. Forwarding and hazard handling mechanisms are incorporated to improve pipeline efficiency and maintain correct operation. The development flow included RTL implementation in Verilog, functional simulation using directed instruction-level test cases, and FPGA-oriented synthesis and analysis in Xilinx Vivado for timing, power, and resource evaluation.

The design achieved successful timing closure with low resource utilization and low dynamic power consumption,

demonstrating suitability for low-power FPGA-based embedded applications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.3:-Behavioral Simulation (Xilinx Vivado)

The Vivado behavioral simulation waveform displays key processor signals over the simulation interval, confirming correct pipeline operation. The clock toggles consistently while the reset signal initializes the processor at the beginning of execution. Signals such as instruction_data, pc_address,

alu_out_address, and store_data transition correctly through the pipeline stages during instruction execution. The branch prediction signals including history, weights, and sum also update dynamically, verifying the operation of the micro-perceptron branch prediction unit within the processor pipeline.

Fig.4:-On Chip Power Analysis Report

The Vivado power report shows a total on-chip power of 0.143 W, broken down into dynamic (9%) and device static (91%) components. The on-chip power chart clearly indicates that signals and logic contribute the most to dynamic power, while clock power remains negligible. The junction temperature reads 25.3°C with a healthy thermal margin, confirming the

design operates safely and efficiently within the FPGA's power limits. The low dynamic power consumption demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed low-power pipelined architecture. These results indicate that the processor is suitable for energy-efficient FPGA-based embedded and edge computing applications.

Design Timing Summary

Setup	Hold	Pulse Width
Worst Negative Slack (WNS): 7.002 ns	Worst Hold Slack (WHS): 0.133 ns	Worst Pulse Width Slack (WPWS): 48.500 ns
Total Negative Slack (TNS): 0.000 ns	Total Hold Slack (THS): 0.000 ns	Total Pulse Width Negative Slack (TPWS): 0.000 ns
Number of Failing Endpoints: 0	Number of Failing Endpoints: 0	Number of Failing Endpoints: 0
Total Number of Endpoints: 494	Total Number of Endpoints: 494	Total Number of Endpoints: 294

All user specified timing constraints are met.

Fig.5:-Design Timing Analysis

The Design Timing Summary in Vivado shows positive slack values across all setup, hold, and pulse width checks with zero failing endpoints out of 494 total. The report explicitly states that all user-

specified timing constraints are met, confirming the processor's data path and pipeline registers are correctly designed to operate at the target clock frequency without any violations.

Fig.6:-FPGA Resource Utilization Summary

The utilization summary in Vivado presents a table alongside a horizontal bar chart showing resource usage percentages. All resources LUTs, Flip-Flops, BRAM,

DSP, and I/O show very low utilization, with bars barely extending past the origin, visually confirming how efficiently the processor fits within the FPGA fabric.

Fig. 7:-FPGA Device Floor plan View

The Vivado device view shows the physical placement of the implemented logic across the FPGA fabric. The teal-colored logic blocks are visibly concentrated in clock regions X0Y1 and X0Y2, while the rest of the device

remains largely empty. This compact and clean placement reflects the low resource utilization of the design and confirms successful place-and-route without any congestion issues.

Fig.8:- RISC V implementation on Basys 3 Board

The proposed RV32I pipelined RISC-V processor was successfully implemented and verified on the Basys 3 FPGA Trainer Board. The onboard LEDs display

continuously incrementing Program Counter (PC) values, confirming correct instruction fetching and sequential execution of instructions through the

pipeline stages. During reset operation, the seven-segment display shows “0000”, indicating proper processor initialization and successful reset functionality.

FUTURE TRENDS

Future enhancements to the proposed processor can focus on improving both performance and functionality. The current design partially handles control hazards and does not fully address load-use hazards; therefore, complete forwarding and stall-based hazard resolution mechanisms can be incorporated for improved execution correctness. Integrating instruction and data caches can reduce memory access latency and enhance processor throughput.

The existing AI-assisted branch predictor can also be upgraded using more advanced machine learning techniques to achieve higher prediction accuracy and minimize pipeline flushes. In addition, the processor may be extended beyond the RV32I base instruction set to support standard extensions such as multiplication, floating-point, and compressed instructions. The architecture can further be scaled into a multi-core design with shared memory and inter-core communication for high-performance embedded and parallel processing applications.

CONCLUSION

This project successfully demonstrates the design, verification, and FPGA implementation of a 32-bit, five-stage pipelined RISC-V processor based on the RV32I base integer instruction set. The processor was described using Verilog HDL and validated through functional simulation, synthesis, implementation, and FPGA design tool analysis using AMD Vivado. The behavioral simulation confirmed the correct operation of all pipeline stages, with key signals transitioning as expected during instruction execution. Timing analysis

showed that all user-defined timing constraints were satisfied with a positive worst negative slack (WNS) of 7.082 ns, indicating reliable design performance.

Resource utilization analysis confirmed an area-efficient implementation, occupying only 4.12% of the available LUT resources, while power analysis reported a total on-chip power consumption of 0.143 W with very low dynamic power consumption. The design was successfully synthesized, implemented, and prepared for deployment on the Basys 3 FPGA Trainer Board, validating the practical feasibility of the proposed architecture. Overall, the project achieves its objectives of developing a functionally correct, timing-compliant, power-efficient, and resource-efficient pipelined RISC-V processor with AI-assisted low-power enhancement.

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